

Assessment of Holy Angel University – School of Engineering and Architecture Administrators as Transformational and Servant Leaders

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ABSTRACT: The leadership style of an individual is influenced by his personality, ability, and skills. Two leadership styles were focused in this study which are transformational and servant leaderships. The level of leaderships of the administrators of the School of Engineering and Architecture (SEA) at Holy Angel University (HAU) for the First Semester School Year 2022-2023 were assessed using self-assessment transformational and servant leadership questionnaires. The assessment resulted that administrative ability is the dominant transformational leader characteristic of the respondents while being creative was the lowest transformational leader characteristic, but still within the high range of the score interpretation. Demonstrating ethical behaviour is the dominant servant leader characteristic but creating value for the community got the lowest characteristic, but still within the moderate range of the score interpretation. The HAU-SEA administrators generally demonstrated the characteristics of a transformational leader and mostly exhibited the behaviours of a servant leader, specifically the exemplary demonstration of ethical behaviours.

KEYWORDS: Leadership, Management, Transformational Leader, Servant Leader

I. INTRODUCTION

In an academic institution, it is desirable that the administrators are transformational and servant leaders because they are dealing with different stakeholders comprising of students, parents, and teachers. There are different leadership styles that the administrators can implement but only two were focused on this study that could be applied in interacting with the stakeholders.

Leadership style is unique in every leader. Even in an organization, different leaders possess different styles because of individual differences. Some prefer to be transformational; others are transactional, some may be servant and others are autocratic leaders. The personalities of an individual determine his leadership style, it cannot be forced nor obliged to someone just to become the ideal leader the organization had perceived.

Northouse (2016) said that leadership has been conceptualized as a trait or behaviour, has been viewed from an information-processing perspective, skills perspective or relational standpoint and has been defined in terms of existing power relationship between leaders and followers. Leadership is a process where an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal.

It can be noted from Northouse (2016) that transformational leadership is a process that changes and transforms people, it is concerned with emotions, values, ethics, standard and

long-term goals. This type of leadership could be implemented to an academic institution where the leader is attentive to the needs and motives of the students and focused in helping them reaching their goals.

According to Northouse (2016), servant leadership is an approach focusing on the concerns of the followers, empathizing with them, and nurturing them. Servant leaders put followers first, empower them and help them develop their full personal capacities. As said by Horsman (2018), servant-conscious leader arises from serving first, naturally transforming and inspired by compassion, generosity, gratitude, and joy. These are the ideal attributes that could be accounted in serving stakeholders. In an academic institution, a servant leader focuses on the students, it is about hope, care, growth and success of the students and the university.

THEORETICAL/CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1. Dependent and Independent Variables

As seen in Figure 1, the independent variable of the study was the demographic profile of the HAU-SEA administrators in terms of gender, civil status, program and educational attainment. Two dependent variables were used to measure the level of leadership in terms of transformational and servant leaderships. The assessment for transformational leadership includes administrative, analytical, performer, energetic, empowering, creative, visionary, and community-builder attributes and the assessment for servant leadership includes emotional healing, creating value for the community, conceptualizing, empowering, helping followers grow and succeed, putting followers first and behaving ethically.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study is limited only to two leadership styles namely transformational and servant leaderships. The administrators of the School of Engineering and Architecture at Holy Angel University for the First Semester School Year 2022-2023 are the respondents for this study, the previous administrators are not included as respondents. The result of this study is limited to the responses of the administrators as they evaluate themselves using self-assessment questionnaires for transformational and servant leadership styles. The result may be biased because it is based on self-assessment, how the respondents see themselves with regards to the areas provided in each leadership style. It will determine the weak and strong areas of the respondents for each leadership style. This study does not reflect the leadership style of the whole university, nor the measure of leadership of the previous and the future administrators of HAU-SEA.

Significance of the Study

The research is important as it will determine the level of transformational and servant leaderships of the administrators of the School of Engineering and Architecture at Holy Angel University for the First Semester School Year 2022-2023. It will define the areas that are weak and strong based on the result of the survey. It will identify the areas that need to be developed and improved if transformational and servant leaderships are the leadership styles that the School of Engineering and Architecture transpires. It will measure the level of transformational leadership of the HAU-SEA administrators in terms of administrative, analytical, performer, energetic, empowering, creative, visionary, and community-builder attributes. It will also measure the level of servant leadership in terms of emotional healing, creating value for the community, conceptualizing, empowering, helping followers grow and succeed, putting followers first and behaving ethically. This study will help the colleagues and students in dealing with the administrators possessing transformational and servant leadership styles.

II. METHODS AND PROCEDURES

Research Design

A descriptive method of research was used in this study. According to Creswell (2014), the said research method is very appropriate for the studies which seek to investigate the nature of the problem using application of the survey method in drawing up the opinions of the respondents. In this study, the said research method was useful to assess if the administrators of Holy Angel University – School of Engineering and Architecture are showing characteristics of being transformational and servant leaders. The descriptive method often involves extensive observation and note-taking, as well as in depth narrative. According to Valdez (2002), descriptive research is concerned with the description of data and characteristics about a population. The goal is the acquisition of factual, accurate and systematic data that can be used in averages, frequencies, and similar statistical calculations. The said research method was the method of choice to meet the objective. A constructive questionnaire via google form was used in the data collection.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Holy Angel University in Angeles City, under the School of Engineering and Architecture.

Samples and Sampling Procedure

This study used a non-probability sampling technique called convenience sampling since the samples has already been identified and not randomly selected. All the administrators of HAU-SEA for the First Semester of School Year 2022-2023 who answered the survey questionnaire for the transformational and servant leadership assessments are the respondents of this study.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study consisted of the administrators from Holy Angel University – School of Engineering and Architecture for the First Semester School Year 2022-2023. These respondents include architects and engineers of the said administration. The study revolved around 11 respondents for the transformational leadership assessment and 10 respondents for the servant leadership assessment that would represent the entire administrators of the School of Engineering and Architecture. The samples represented the population to arrive at a valid conclusion and decision to collect, organize and summarize the data systematically. The findings would be limited to Holy Angel University – School of Engineering and Architecture involved in this study.

Research Instruments

The primary tool used in gathering data was the survey questionnaire. Using the questionnaire, the necessary data

was obtained. This is to test whether the administrators of the School of Engineering and Architecture are transformational and servant leaders. The research instrument of the survey questionnaire included two parts.

Part I is for the Transformational Leadership Questionnaire that includes questions about how you individually like to work, how you like to work on teams and how you like to work on major projects using a 7-point Scale. Scale of 1 means that the statement or question does not describe you at all, Scale of 3 means that the statement or question describes you occasionally, Scale of 5 means that the statement or question describes you a lot of the time and a Scale of 7 means that the statement or question describes you all the time. Each question corresponds to the eight characteristics of transformational leadership as administrative, analytical, performer, energetic, empowering, creative, visionary and community builder.

Part II is for Servant Leadership Questionnaire that includes questions that will show the degree to which the respondent exhibits the characteristics of a servant leader. It also uses a 7-point Scale.

Data Gathering Procedure

The questionnaires' link was sent to the administrators of the School of Engineering and Architecture. They were given a week to complete and accomplish the questionnaire.

Data Analysis Technique

The gathered data was automatically compiled, sorted out, and tabulated because a google form was used for the survey questionnaire. Graphical representation was created via Google Data Studio.

To quantify and determine the Transformational and Servant Leader Characteristics of the administrators of the School of Engineering and Architecture, the researchers tabulated and interpreted the responses using 7-point Scale and the interpretation would be as follows:

For the Transformational Leadership Questionnaire:

- 1 - That doesn't describe me at all
- 2 - Answer between 1 and 3
- 3 - That describes me occasionally
- 4 - Answer between 3 and 5
- 5 - That describes me a lot of the time
- 6 - Answer between 5 and 7
- 7 - That describes me all the time

Each question in the survey corresponds with one of the eight characteristics of transformational leadership. The questions corresponding with each transformational leadership characteristic are as follows:

Administrative (14 questions) 5, 10, 14, 16, 27, 29, 46, 52, 55, 58, 64, 68, 72, 76

Analytical (12 questions) 11, 18, 20, 25, 31, 38, 45, 57, 78, 82, 84, 87

Performer (13 questions) 1, 2, 3, 7, 13, 15, 32, 43, 54, 59, 83, 85, 86

Energetic (8 questions) 6, 17, 23, 42, 51, 53, 66, 80

Empowering (10 questions) 4, 19, 26, 37, 40, 47, 74, 77, 79, 88

Creative (10 questions) 8, 21, 28, 33, 34, 36, 61, 71, 75, 81

Visionary (10 questions) 9, 22, 30, 35, 39, 48, 49, 62, 67, 70

Community-Builder (11 questions) 12, 24, 41, 44, 50, 56, 60, 63, 65, 69, 73

For each characteristic, total the responses (1–7) for each question and then divide the total by the number of questions for that characteristic. For example, if the total response for the administrative characteristic is 70, divide 70 by the total number questions for that characteristic. For the administrative characteristic, the total is 14 questions. In this example, the average score for the administrative area is 5 on a scale of 1–7. Those characteristics with the highest average score would be considered as the administrator's strengths. Those with the lowest average score would be the learning opportunities. The administrators should consider what actions to take in at least two of the learning opportunity areas and develop a personal improvement plan.

For Servant Leadership Questionnaire:

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 3 - Disagree Somewhat
- 4 - Undecided
- 5 - Agree Somewhat
- 6 - Agree
- 7 - Strongly Agree

Scoring:

Add up the scores on 1, 8, 15, and 22. This is your score for emotional healing.

Add up the scores for 2, 9, 16, and 23. This is your score for creating value for the community.

Add up the scores for 3, 10, 17, and 24. This is your score for conceptual skills.

Add up the scores for 4, 11, 18, and 25. This is your score for empowering.

Add up the scores for 5, 12, 19, and 26. This is your score for helping subordinates grow and succeed.

Add up the scores for 6, 13, 20, and 27. This is your score for putting subordinates first.

Add up the scores for 7, 14, 21, and 28. This is your score for behaving ethically.

Scoring Interpretation:

High range: A score between 23 and 28 means you strongly exhibit this servant leadership behavior.

Moderate range: A score between 14 and 22 means you tend to exhibit this behavior in an average way.

Low range: A score between 8 and 13 means you exhibit this leadership below the average or expected degree.

Extremely low range: A score between 0 and 7 means you are not inclined to exhibit this leadership behavior at all. The scores on the Servant Leadership Self-Assessment Questionnaire indicated the degree to which the administrators of School of Engineering and Architecture exhibited the seven behaviors characteristic of a servant leader. The results were used to assess areas in which they have strong servant leadership behaviors and areas in which they may strive to improve.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Part 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

This part includes the demographic profile of the administrators in terms of program, gender, educational attainment, and civil status. The administrators who responded to the survey questionnaire of transformational and servant leaderships are composed of architects and engineers.

Transformational Leadership

There are 11 administrators who answered the survey questionnaire for the transformational leadership assessment under the HAU-SEA. Figure 2 shows the percentage of the respondents in each program. From the respondents, 36.36% are Electronics Engineers, 18.18% are Electrical Engineers, 18.18% are Civil Engineers, 9.09% are Aeronautical Engineers, 9.09% are Industrial Engineers and 9.09% are Architects.

Figure 2. Distribution of HAU-SEA administrators in programs for transformational leadership assessment

Gender: Among the 11 respondents, as seen in Table 1, 8 are male and 3 are female. It could be seen that 72.73% came from the male group and 27.27% came from the female group.

Table 1. Frequency distribution of the demographic profile of the administrators for transformational leadership assessment

Profile	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	8	72.73
Female	3	27.27
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	4	36.36
Master's Degree	6	54.55
Doctorate Degree	1	9.09
Civil Status		
Married	6	54.55
Single	5	45.45

Educational Attainment: From Table 1, only 1 administrator is a graduate of a doctorate degree, leading to 9.09% of the respondents. It could be seen that 6 are holder of master's degree, which is 54.55% and the remaining 36.36% comprises the bachelor's degree holder, which are 4 respondents.

Civil Status: Table 1 shows the distribution of the administrators by civil status. It shows that among the 11 respondents, 6 are married, which is 54.55%, and 5 are single, which is 45.45% of the sample group.

Servant Leadership

There are 10 administrators who responded to the survey questionnaire of servant leadership assessment. As presented in Figure 3, the distribution is composed of 40% who are Electronics Engineers, 10% are Architects, 10% are Industrial Engineers, 10% are Civil Engineers, 10% are Aeronautical Engineers, and 20% are Electrical Engineers.

Figure 3. Distribution of HAU-SEA administrators in programs for servant leadership assessment

Gender: Among the 10 respondents, Table 2 shows that 7 are male and 3 are female from the sample group of servant leadership assessment. The HAU-SEA administration is

dominated by the male group of 70% and 30% is from the female group.

Table 2. Frequency distribution of the demographic profile of the administrators for servant leadership assessment

Profile	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	7	70.00
Female	3	30.00
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor’s Degree	4	40.00
Master’s Degree	5	50.00
Doctorate Degree	1	10
Civil Status		
Married	6	60.00
Single	4	40.00

Educational Attainment: Table 2 shows that 1 out of 10 respondents is a graduate of doctorate degree, which is 10% of the sample, 40% are bachelor’s degree holder, which are 4 respondents, and 50% are master’s degree holder, which are 5 respondents.

Civil Status: As depicted in Table 2, 60% are married respondents from the HAU-SEA administration, comprising of 6 respondents. Only 40% are single from the sample, which are 4 respondents.

Part 2. Descriptive Statistic of the Level of Transformational Leadership

The data gathered by the researchers shown in Tables 3 and 4 that, on average, the HAU—SEA administrator often describes themselves as demonstrating characteristics of a transformational leader. Administrative ability is the dominant transformational leader characteristic, and vision represents the respondents.

Table 3. Transformational leadership survey results 1

Respondent	Administrative	Analytical	Performer	Energetic
1	5.43	5.33	5.15	5.5
2	5.86	5.67	5.85	5.75
3	6.07	5.92	6.08	6
4	7	6.75	6.69	6.75
5	5.36	5.33	5.62	5.5
6	5.64	5.17	5.08	5.5
7	5.21	5.5	5.23	5.13
8	6.57	5.33	6.08	6.5
9	4.71	4.83	4.92	4.38
10	6.5	5.58	5.62	5.88
11	4.86	4.67	4.69	5.25
Mean	5.75	5.46	5.55	5.65
Std. Dev.	0.73	0.56	0.60	0.65
Skewness	0.29	1.04	0.43	-0.11
Kurtosis	-0.86	2.28	-0.37	0.66

Table 4. Transformational leadership survey results 2

Respondent	Empowering	Creative	Visionary	Community-BUILDER
1	4.9	3.4	4.7	5.09
2	5.9	5.3	5.3	5.64
3	5.9	6.1	6.1	6.27
4	7	6.8	7	7
5	5.3	5.5	5.2	5.36
6	5.6	5.5	5.7	5.45
7	5.3	4.8	5	5
8	6.4	5.9	4.9	5.91
9	4.3	4.4	4.4	3.36
10	6	5.6	6	6.18
11	5	4.4	4.4	4.45
Mean	5.60	5.25	5.34	5.43
Std. Dev.	0.75	0.94	0.80	0.98
Skewness	0.16	-0.42	0.80	-0.64
Kurtosis	0.15	0.32	0.28	1.10

Part 3. Descriptive Statistic of the Level of Servant Leadership

As presented in Tables 5 and 6, the HAU—SEA administrator self-evaluation on servant leadership generally shows that the administrators believe that they strongly exhibit the seven behaviors of a servant leader where the majority demonstrates exemplary ethical behavior and creates value for the community getting the lowest mean but still within the high range of the score interpretation.

Table 5. Servant leadership survey result 1

Respondent	Emotional Healing	Creating Value for Community	Conceptualizing
1	26	18	24
2	22	23	22
3	25	24	23
4	23	23	22
5	20	21	22
6	24	22	22
7	24	26	25
8	19	18	21
9	25	19	23
10	27	26	22
Mean	23.50	22.00	22.60
Std. Dev.	2.55	2.98	1.17
Skewness	-0.60	-0.09	0.99
Kurtosis	-0.39	-1.23	0.75

Table 6. Servant leadership survey results 2

Respondent	Empowering	Helping Followers Grow and Succeed	Putting Followers First	Behaving Ethically
1	21	24	23	24
2	21	22	20	23
3	24	24	26	26
4	23	25	26	25
5	21	21	21	21
6	19	24	23	26

7	27	26	25	24
8	17	17	17	25
9	26	23	22	26
10	23	26	25	20
11	22.20	23.20	22.80	24.00
Mean	3.05	2.70	2.90	2.11
Std. Dev.	-0.03	-1.41	-0.78	-0.98
Skewness	-0.31	2.39	0.18	-0.05
Kurtosis				

IV. FINDINGS

Transformational leadership and servant leadership are both high-order evolutions in leadership paradigms. Both emphasize a high concern for people. Transformational leaders have a stronger focus on organizational objectives. On the other hand, servant leadership involves a higher concern for people because the primary focus of the leader is upon his or her followers.

The reviewed literature and studies have greatly contributed to the present study. Some studies and literature show that leadership styles of transformational and servant leaders directly affect faculty members' motivation, performance, and innovations, including students. Various researchers support the hypothesis that implementing and learning either transformational or servant leadership provides a significant impact on the management of colleges or any academic institutions.

This study attempted to assess the HAU – SEA Administrators level of Transformational and Servant Leadership. Specifically, the researchers answered the following problems:

1. What is the demographic profile of the HAU-SEA administrators in terms of:
 - 1.1 Gender
 - 1.2 Civil Status
 - 1.3 Program
 - 1.4 Educational Attainment
2. What is the level of transformational leadership of the HAU-SEA administrators?
3. What is the level of servant leadership of the HAU-SEA administrators?

The researchers used the descriptive method in conducting the study. The instruments used to gather the data were a questionnaire/structured survey.

With all the statistical treatments, the researchers listed the following findings:

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The demographic profile of the administrators are as follows: they consist of mostly of male, married and with master's degree.

Level of transformational leadership of the HAU-SEA administrators

The HAU—SEA administrator often describes themselves as demonstrating characteristics of a transformational leader.

Administrative ability is the dominant transformational leader characteristic with a mean of 5.75 and being creative getting the lowest mean of 5.25 but still within the high range of the score interpretation. This means that they have an immense number of skills to facilitate their daily tasks. They transform their knowledge and experiences into actions. They balance their emotions that demonstrate positive characteristics while working as a team.

Level of servant leadership of the HAU-SEA administrators

The HAU—SEA administrator self-evaluation on servant leadership generally shows that the administrators believe that they strongly exhibit the seven behaviours of a servant leader where the majority demonstrates exemplary ethical behaviour with a mean of 24.00 and creates value for the community getting the lowest with a mean of 22.00 but still within the moderate range of the score interpretation. This means that they show integrity, honesty, and are inclined to do the right thing. They display self-confidence that makes people around them feel that they are more inclined to work for a leader they know they can trust to make the right decisions.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Most of the administrators are male that are married, and with master's degree.
2. Administrative ability is the dominant transformational leader characteristic and being creative getting the lowest but still within the high range of the score interpretation.
3. Demonstrating ethical behaviour is the dominant servant leader characteristic and creating value for the community getting the lowest but still within the moderate range of the score interpretation.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

Considering the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were drawn:

1. The respondents should find joy in creating novel solutions to routine problems and tasks.
2. The respondents should enjoy brainstorming new ideas, new ways to implement and execute the project or task in a team setting and make sure everybody's making unique contributions.
3. The respondents should emphasize the importance of giving back and helping people in the community.
4. The respondents should be more involved in community activities and encourage others to volunteer in the community.

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